

PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF AHMAD YASSAWI

Karshieva Yanglish Abduvalievna

Doctoral student of Gulistan State University

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Abstract. *Ahmad Yassawi, a man who knew and comprehended wisdom, understood how to be a real person in the true sense of the word, gain peace of mind and began to strive for spiritual perfection.*

Although a number of scientific studies have been conducted in our country about the life and work of Ahmad Yassawi, there have been no specific studies of the psychological aspects of his mystical views. Despite the fact that the Kubrowia Current originated in Central Asia and has spread widely throughout different countries of the world, the Kubrowia Current has not yet been fully studied. Ahmed Yassawi is a great man who is an example to the whole world with his extraordinary zeal and determination in the pursuit of knowledge, courage in the path of truth, patriotism and generosity. For this reason, it is necessary to carefully examine his life path and spiritual heritage, and we have focused on these aspects in this article.

Keywords: *wisdom of Ahmad Yassawi, views of Eastern thinkers, “Devoni Hikmat”, human psychology, peace of mind, spiritual perfection.*

Introduction. The name of Khoja Ahmed Yassawi, one of the great imams of Sufism, the founder of the Yassawi teaching, who quickly became popular among the masses with his simple, folk Sufi wisdom, is valuable and respected in the Islamic world. He is the one who skillfully developed the integrity of Shariah and Tariqah (directions in religion). A prominent place in the legacy of Ahmed Yasawi is occupied by his collection of poems entitled “Hikmat”. This collection of poems is known in the literary community as Devoni Hikmat. Also, his educational and psychologically valuable views are reflected in the work “Rasail” (“Risola”).

All the principles of the Yassawi order are described in detail in the main work of Ahmad Yassawi, “Hikmat”. The work “Hikmat”, which is an excellent example of Turkic-language poetry of the 12th century and had a great influence on Turkish literature of later periods, reveals purity, honesty, correctness, kindness, self-promotion of universal human values, such as making a living with the strength of hands, foreskin and by honest work, the full improvement of the human being inside and out towards achieving the will of Almighty God.

Ahmed Yassawi's wisdom is varied in subject matter. If we read them sincerely and try to understand, the reader will begin to discover the existence called “Man” and explore himself. This “discovery” (self-awareness) gradually takes the reader away from fleeting whims and desires, to the essence. Encourages humanity. One end of these impulses leads to the simple and popular language of Yassawi wisdom, and the other end is to penetrate the heart with strong artistic expressions and educate the poet both spiritually and artistically. In Yassawi's wisdom, the desire for knowledge, the call for knowledge and enlightenment are the leading words, and the poems emphasize the high value of learned people.

A person who has known and comprehended the wisdom of Ahmed Yassawi understands how to be a real person in the true sense of the word, gains peace of mind and begins to strive for spiritual perfection.

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Literature review

After Uzbekistan gained independence, began a new era in legal research. Initially, copies of *Devoni Hikmat* were published in various newspapers and magazines, and in 1990-1992, 2 independent publications were delivered to readers. These publications increased interest in the life, literary and educational activities of this great mystic, and the followers not only in Uzbekistan, but also in other Turkic countries. In 1993, were held scientific conferences dedicated to Yassawi in Uzbekistan, and the texts of the lectures were published in a separate collection. The press published articles devoted to the personality, teaching and poetry of Yassawi. Several streets and neighborhoods in Uzbekistan are called Yassawi. The foundations of the Yasawi teaching is reflected in such sources and treatises as “Fakrinama” (some attribute it to Yasawi), “Maslakul-arifin”, “Lamaot”, “Samaratul-mashoyih”, “Jawahir ul-Abror”.

According to Yassawi, wisdom is “ilmi laduni,” that is, knowledge of the invisible, and also means the discovery of divine secrets. Yassawi himself did not create a single book called *Devoni Hikmat*. This rare work was commissioned by his murid and followers. But this does not give grounds to assert that the wisdom complex has nothing to do with Yassawi. Commenting on Sufi Olloyar Yassawi, he also said: Sharia was ul oftobe, Kalibdur us ul erdin kitabe.

The book "*Devoni Hikmat*" was organized by Yassawi's students. It is dominated by the idea of divine love and educational content. Proverbs are deeply connected to the Holy Quran and the hadiths of Muhammad, peace be upon him, with attention to meaning and essence. More than 20 copies of “*Devoni Hikmat*” are kept in the collections of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The oldest manuscript of the work dates back to the 17th century.

The Yassawi Legacy and Foreign Teachings L. Massignon, A. Arberry, M. Smith, H. Kisling, F. Mayer, A. Schimmel, R. Hartman, F. Koprulu, J. Trimmingham, K. Eraslon, Idris Schoch, Devin Dee Vis; In Russia A. Krymsky, I. Petrushevsky, E. Bertels; In Uzbekistan, it was studied by Fitrat, A. Saadi, E. Rustamov, B. Kasimov, I. Khakkulov, N. Hasanov.

Research Methodology

Based on the study of Yassawi's wisdom, has been developed a questionnaire to determine the perception of psychological concepts that determine a person's maturity, based on the criterion of factor analysis; it is based on the fact that the comments of the questionnaire are divided into significant and insignificant units;

Based on a psychological analysis of Yassawi's wisdom, it was determined that students and youth exhibit spiritual needs, they are characterized by a variety of moral situations in educational activities, high mobility in mastering tasks, diligence, intelligence, and the ability to control oneself.

Based on the psychological analysis of Yassawi's wisdom, the students were identified with the psychological characteristics of the concept of an ideal person and it was proven that are highly developed the qualities of high faith, perseverance, selflessness towards others, honesty, humility, justice, selflessness, humanism and patriotism.

It has been proven that behavior that overcomes certain situations, that is, perseverance, faith in fate, overcoming reality, self-change, positive thinking, control of emotions, have a positive effect on the formation of qualities characteristic of a perfect person.

A person who is able to understand the wisdom of Ahmad Yassawi, by reading and studying it, begins to achieve peace of mind and spiritual perfection in the true sense. Yassawi's wisdom not only deepens human thinking, but also teaches the true science of humanity.

Yassawi is known as the first Turkic-language mystical poet in the history of Central Asian culture. His poems, written in Turkish, promoting Sufism, quickly became popular due to the intimacy and melodiousness of the language. Khoja Ahmed Yassawi trained many mystical sages. It is known that after the Yassawiyya teaching, two large teaching ways appeared in Central Asia, such as Naqshbandiya (Khojagon) and Bektoshiya.

From some of his wisdom it is clear that Yassawi was not at all interested in accumulating wealth, like his Sheikh Yusuf Hamadani, and lived like a poor man and an outsider. Yassawi unabashedly criticizes greedy people obsessed with wealth, luxury and statehood:

A person who takes the path of lust will be disgraced.

The road is rough, slippery and uneven.

If he falls asleep, if he gets up, he will be with the devil...

Don't worry about the world, don't talk about yourself.

Don't eat other people's property, you will leave them poor.

Woman, relative, companion

Be a brave person, let your life fly like the wind.

Kul Khoja Ahmed obey, I don't know how many years you will live.

If you really know it's clay, it will be clay again.

In fact, Khoja Ahmed Yassawi is the founder of the first mystical order in Central Asia - "Yassaviya", a mystic sage, poet-humanist, widely known in the spiritual history of not only Khorasan and Mavarunnahr, but also the Turkic-speaking peoples.

Analysis and results

Ahmed Yassawi skillfully interpreted the tenets of Islam, using his wisdom, tried to guide people on the right path. And a person who follows this path will go to peace of mind and spiritual perfection. The purpose of writing this article is to once again remind you that Yassawi's wisdom occupies an incomparable place in the sense that people want to be mentally calm and spiritually perfect.

I was worried about you

I opened the door of truth.

I have entered the treasury of truth,

I scattered the gems.

Khoja Ahmed Yassawi is a famous representative of Turkish mystical poetry. He became famous and popular in several countries of the world due to his work "Devoni Hikmat". My grandfather Mashrab said in one of his ghazals: "My soul has reached the throne, I am the sky." In this sense, Yassawi is one of the leaders of poets like Mashrab, the sage of the Supreme Spirit, whose spiritual world is complex and contradictory, and this is reflected in all its depth in his work. Yassawi's view of the world is different from the views of people of our time. There is no doubt that Yassawi's approach to issues such as love, truth, justice, satisfaction and religion went in different directions. Being a child of his time, he relied on the principles of Islam.

About Alisher Navoi Yassawi, he says: "His authority is high and famous, his merits are outstanding and inglorious. He is an excellent student and comrade, and he is extremely humble before the will and sincerity of the king." This idea dates back to the time when Yassawi returned to Iasi and became famous as a murshid who founded a new sect. Yassawi also used poetry to attract more Turkic peoples to Islam and deeply instill the ideas of Sufism into the hearts of the masses. Abdurauf Fitrat said that "Yasawi's path in literature is the dark path of our simple folk poets... His wisdom is equal in weight, rhyme and style to the poems called folk literature." He wrote a work that will become a warning not only to the Turkish people, but to the whole world. The study of his wisdom, conveying to people the true meaning of wisdom remains one of the most pressing issues.

Conclusion/ Recommendations

The work of Ahmad Yassawi also left a rich spiritual heritage in terms of understanding the human personality, understanding the spiritual world and ways of manifesting oneself in existence. His richest legacy is the wisdom of Devoni Hikmat.

"Devoni Hikmat" protects a person from selfishness, ignorance and predation. "Devoni Hikmat" influences the spiritual world of humanity, protects it from satanic tricks, animal attacks and helps to achieve peace of mind and spiritual perfection. This invaluable work warns of the difficulties and evils of greed and "eating humanity clean."

It's all a matter of how to read it and how to realize it, and act with awareness.

All the principles of the Yassawi order are described in detail in the main work of Ahmad Yassawi, "Hikmat". The work "Hikmat", which is an excellent example of Turkic-language poetry of the 12th century and had a great influence on Turkish literature of later periods, shows purity, honesty, correctness, kindness, strength of labor, and expresses advanced universal values, such as the internal and external improvement of man in all aspects on the path to achieving the will of Allah.

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